

Understanding the background of India-China relations

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Abstract

Today the relations between India and China have become so sore that the armies of both the countries are face to face on the border. Everyday there are reports of conflict in the Galwan valley and sometimes the skirmishes at Pangong Tso lake, make headlines but there was a time when there was a very deep friendship between the two countries, the roots of this friendship can be seen in thousands of years old history

Introduction

If we put in simple words, before the conflict of 1962, there were strong economic religious cultural relations between the two countries for about 2000 years. There are evidence that ideological and linguistic exchanges existed between the old Chinese civilization of China and The Vedic civilization of India between 1500 and 1000 BCE. By the Second century BC the southern branch of the Silk Road connected China and India during the. Many Buddhist pilgrims and Scholars traveled to China along this historic Silk Road. Ancient monk scholars such as contributed to the spread of Buddhism in China. Similarly, Chinese pilgrims also made visits to India. Among these the names of Chinese travelers like Hiuen Tsang and Fa-Hien. This age old relationships continued till the modern times. Later on both the countries become victims of

imperialist exploitation. After getting rid of this both of them started trying to keep the imperialist powers out of Asia (Baru, 2012).

Apart from this after the formation of the People's Republic of China, India gave it the highest priority. The situation was that India was advocating the People's Republic of China by going to Global Forums in return the Chinese leaders were colluding with the Indian leaders. The leaders of both the countries were visiting each other. Such was the friendship for a full decade before China conducted its nuclear test in September 1964. Chinese leader Mao Zedong Shared important information with the then Indian Prime Minister Jawaharlal Nehru. He had told Prime Minister Nehru that China had intended to make an atomic bomb; this was such information which Intelligence agencies around the world were trying hard to know. But Mao Zedong casually mentioned it in conversation with Nehru, this shows how strong the relationship was between the two countries, but who knew that one day these relations would turn sore and that both the countries would not be able to trust each other (Mohan, 2013)

Deteriorating relations between India and China

On 15th August 1947, India becomes independent; on the other hand the Communist Party of China captured the power in January 1948 by showing the way out to the Nationalist party. Communist party leader Mao Zedong declares the country as the People's Republic of China that is what is known as China today since Jawaharlal Nehru one of the prominent leaders of the movement before India's independence always emphasized on Sino-Indian friendship; also many leaders of India had a liberal attitude towards communism. So when the communist gained power in China it was widely welcomed in India not only this India went a step ahead and became the first non-communist country to recognize the People's Republic of China in

December 1949. Further India was also the first non-communist country to establish diplomatic relations with the People's Republic of China in April 1950. Basically, Indian Policy towards China was based on several assumptions. First, of all there have been strong cultural and economic ties between the two countries since the Indus Valley Civilization as we have already mentioned. Second, both the countries have faced atrocities of foreign imperialism. When the Chinese were invaded by Japan, Indians had a feeling of sympathy and respect for the Chinese people. Third, the Indian leaders believed that China would continue to maintain good relations. India did not participate in the International peace treaty conference with Japan held in San Francisco in the year 1949. This is because China was not invited and about 49 countries participated in this conference. In June 1954 India and China together sign Panchsheel Agreement. Under the Panchsheel principle mutual respect to each other's territorial integrity and sovereignty Mutual non-aggression, non-interference in each other's internal affairs equality and cooperation and peaceful cooperation were included (Bajpai, 2010) .

In July 1954, the Indian Prime Minister writes a memorandum directing the amendment of the map to show the definite boundary of India. About 1 lakh 20 thousand square kilometers of Indian Territory was shown as a part of China on the Chinese map. However, when China is asked a question on this, Chinese Prime Minister Zhou Enlai replies that there was a mistake in that map, from here begins the real story of the weakening of the relationship between the two countries. In the year 1955, Nehru and Zhou meet during the Afro-Asian Conference in Bandung Indonesia. Here Zhou made a tremendous impact on other countries of Asia with his words. In fact Zhou had set out to make new friends in Asia, in this period China became close with Pakistan. This was the conference from where the slogan of 'Hindi Chini Bhai Bhai' started fading away. Meanwhile, China and Pakistan relations reached a positive phase. The distance

between India and China started increasing. During, the Tibetan insurgency in 1959, fearing for their lives Buddhist monk Dalai Lama and his followers fled to India. The tension between the two countries escalated when Mao said that the Tibet rebellion was caused by India. Tibet became a major reason for enmity between the two countries. This culminated into military conflict between India and China in 1962. On 10 July 1962 around 350 soldiers surrounded the Indian post in Ladakh they then used loud speakers to convince the Gurkhas that they should not fight for India. Finally on October 20, 1962 this resulted into tensions between India and China in the form of war (Pant, 2012) .

Conclusion

Thus, the friendship of the two emerging superpowers of the 21st century turned into enmity. The old relationship between the two Asian Giants collapsed. However bilateral relations between the two countries were restored again in the 1980s. In 1993, during the visit of Indian Prime Minister Narasimha Rao, an agreement was reached to maintain peace along the Line of Actual Control (LAC) on the India-China border. Today China is India's largest trading partner, yet China always shows its valor on various issues ranging from its claim on Indian State of Arunachal Pradesh to building military bases in India's neighboring countries. There is also a fact that both the countries are competing to become the undisputed superpower of Asia this is the reason why they are suspicious of each other's intentions. At the same time, China always supports Pakistan against India due to which India is not happy.

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